

XiA Community of Practice

Building a European community to strengthen interoperability skills in digital health

A collaborative ecosystem for digital health interoperability

Why join XiA Community of Practice?

Access expertise

Interoperability standards such as HL7 FHIR and EEHRxF

Connect across Europe

Join a network of healthcare and policy experts

Develop skills

Participate in training activities and knowledge exchange

Support EHDS

Promote interoperable health systems in Europe

Join the XiA Community of Practice

Register your interest and join the interoperability ecosystem

1 Leverage workforce in interoperability
Define interoperability curricula aligned with workforce needs

2 Map learning needs and digital skills
Map key interoperability, digital health and cybersecurity skills

3 Create online learning content & communities
Develop modular learning content and communities of practice

4 Credentialing schema accreditation & QA
Establish accreditation and quality assurance frameworks

5 Integrate interoperability cybersecurity & digital transformation
Embed EHDS, interoperability and cybersecurity into training

6 Implement micro-credentials and academic certification
Deliver micro-credentials and recognised certification pathways

Project overview

Duration : 48 months / Jan 2025 - Dec 2028

Objective : Bridging the skills gap in **digital health interoperability** and creating a **sustainable European training framework**

Partners : 42 organisations - universities, hospitals, SMEs and industry leaders

Countries : 19 EU countries

Budget : € 3,98 million

And 25 Associated Partners

